

Towards a Sustainable Nigeria National Soil Information System (NiSIS) The Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel

21st – 23rd October 2025, Abuja, Nigeria

Workshop report

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List of Abbreviation

FMAFS	Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security
ALCCMS	Agricultural Land and Climate Change Management Services
SIS	Soil Information System
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
CABI	Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
SCH	Soil Health Card
DST	Decision Support Tool
GIS	Geographic Information System
RA	Readiness Assessment
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
EU	European Union
NiSIS	Nigeria National Soil Information System
NOT	Nutrient omission trial
CoW	Coalition of the Willing
SOP	Standard operation procedures
SIWF	Soil information workflow
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FAO	Food and Agriculture organisation
IFDC	International fertilizer development centre
AGRA	Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa

Executive Summary

This SIS development report outlines the strategic steps for building and strengthening Nigeria's Soil Information System (NiSIS) to enhance agricultural productivity, soil health, and informed decision-making for sustainable soil management. It builds on insights from the "Nigeria Soil Information System Development Workshop" held in October 2025 in Abuja, Nigeria, hosted by Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, IITA Nigeria and ISRIC-World Soil Information. Participants from various sectors addressed common data and capacity challenges and discussed long-term financial sustainability options for NiSIS.

The workshop reviewed six components thought to be crucial for NiSIS's success: 1) Understanding of current SIS status, 2) Exploring FAIR data compliance and governance, 3) Exploring technical options for sustainable operation, 4) Identifying ways of strategic planning for long-term NiSIS, 5) Exploring standardized SOPs, and 6) Agreeing on next steps for the development of the SIS. The roadmap includes an overview of each component, addressing available information, gaps, and recommendations, which are optional for the NiSIS project team to consider.

The key potential next steps for Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security FMAFS, CoW and IITA to consider include:

- Development of soil and data policy draft for NiSIS.
- Further develop the RA- CoW for data, lab, field, technical, and policy assessment.
- Review and suggest improvements to the current data sharing protocol, acting upon suggestions provided by group discussion.
- Development of data policy including updated data sharing agreement .
- Develop MoU between IITA & FMAFS.
- Readiness (being fully prepared or willing to act) NFSHS-NiSIS by the remaining states.
- Adapt the agreed upon SOPs for labs and field sampling.
- Improve the NiSIS existing geoportal.
- Capacity building on different domains in NiSIS.
- Conduct a National soil survey/nutrient omission trial NOT.

Acknowledgments

FMAFS, ISRIC-World Soil Information, Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA would like to thank workshop participants for their contributions that have led to the development of this roadmap. With special thanks to Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA for their support in organizing the workshop, and to CABI for their input and review.

More information, supporting resources and useful tools for each of the components are available in the online SIS framework, hosted on ISRIC's Resource Library and created by CABI and ISRIC – World Soil Information (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>).

If there are any questions or aspects of the roadmap that require further support or input from ISRIC, kindly contact chrow.khurshid@isric.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org.

Introduction

A Soil Information System (SIS) is not just a digital platform but a collaborative tool that engages stakeholders, from government agencies to farmers, to improve data access, soil health management, and informed decision-making in Nigeria's agriculture sector. Understanding how these people and institutions should work together, and aligning on who is responsible for what, is a critical step to ensuring the progress of the SIS. There are three levels of the broader enabling environment for the system that need to be considered: the individual (suitable skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes), the organizational (efficient structures, processes, and procedures), and the governmental level (establishment of adequate institutions, laws, and regulations).

[CAB-International](#) and [ISRIC – World Soil Information](#), supported by the Gates Foundation, has created a framework for SIS development, assessing these levels at the start of a SIS intervention. The [SIS Framework](#) helps to identify activities needed to fulfil the objectives set for a SIS, deciding also on the sequence in which these activities are best performed, who is going to do them, and identifying potential risks, with each specifically tailored to the country context. The SIS framework was used as the base resource for the NiSIS development workshop which was held in October 2025 in Abuja, Nigeria.

The objectives of the NiSIS development workshop were:

- Understanding current SIS status.
- Exploring FAIR data compliance and governance.
- Exploring technical options for sustainable operation.
- Identifying ways for strategic planning for a long-term NiSIS.
- Exploring standardized standard operating procedures (SOPs).
- Agreeing on next steps for the development of the SIS.

This document gathers the information collected and validated during the workshop that details the steps required to achieve a specific goal, namely achievement of *a sustainable national SIS in Nigeria that will last beyond the initial phases of project funding, be built on best practices, and continue to meet the needs of users.*

Workshop Day 1:

The workshop commenced with welcome remarks from Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (FMAFS). This was followed by an introduction of participants and an overview of the program and its expected outputs by IITA.

Session 1 – Setting the Scene

The session started with FMAFS remarks on the need for SIS by Director Agricultural Land and Climate Change Management Services ALCCMS & Soil Health Card HMS-FMAFS. Followed by short presentations on AfSIS/NiSIS with a demonstration by Prof. Vincent, and presentations on NiSIS current state by Prof James Jayeoba, and soil health cards' link with NiSIS by Prof J.M. Jibrin.

A summary of all presentations as below:

The initial presentations by the CoW and RA addressed the progress and necessary next steps for the Coalition of the Willing (CoW) and Readiness Assessment (RA) initiatives supporting Nigeria's Soil Information System (NiSIS) and the National Fertilizer and Soil Health Strategy (NFSHS). The CoW aims to accelerate soil data integration, capacity building, and policy advocacy through thematic working groups, while RA evaluates state preparedness for implementing the NFSHS. Pilot assessments in Nasarawa, Ebonyi, and Oyo revealed varying readiness and policy gaps. Both initiatives work in synergy, RA identifies gaps and the CoW develops solutions. Stakeholders include federal and state governments, research bodies, private sector partners, and farmers. Next steps (2025–2026) include finalizing NiSIS–NFSHS integration, expanding state participation, conducting assessments in 10 more states, and publishing a National Soil Health Readiness & CoW Report by 2026.

The presentation “Soil Health Card Link” by J.M. Jibrin explained the concept of a Soil Health Card (SHC). A simple, farmer-friendly report translating soil test results into crop-specific fertilizer and amendment recommendations. It reviews SHC implementations in countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Kenya, and Ethiopia, noting that India's 2015 national program remains the most comprehensive. Key lessons from India include the importance of clear design, farmer-centered communication, and pairing cards with advisory services and incentives to drive real behaviour change. Nigeria's NFSHS could adopt a similar phased, quality-controlled approach starting with priority areas, ensuring lab and sampling standards, aligning card delivery with planting seasons, and measuring actual impacts on farmer practices and productivity.

The presentation “AfSIS–NiSIS Beginning” detailed the origin and evolution of Nigeria's Soil Information System (NiSIS) as part of the broader Africa Soil Information Service (AfSIS)

initiative. AfSIS, funded by the Gates Foundation, aimed to improve soil management across Africa through digital mapping, data integration, and capacity building. Nigeria joined during Phase I (2008–2013) with soil surveys and trials in sentinel sites and continued into Phase II (2014–2018) to establish NiSIS officially in 2017. NiSIS focuses on tackling soil fertility constraints, building national soil databases, and strengthening analytical and collaborative capacity. Despite challenges such as funding and bureaucracy, NiSIS has advanced soil data collection in states such as Kebbi and Ebonyi and contributed to digital mapping and research publications.

The Data integration protocols & standards presentation outlined a unified framework for integrating soil and land datasets into the NiSIS under the Coalition of the Willing (CoW). It establishes guidelines for data submission, ownership, quality assurance, and accessibility to ensure datasets from various sources are harmonized, interoperable, and reliable for policy, research, and farmer advisory use. Key standards cover file formats, metadata, coordinate systems (WGS84), and soil classification (FAO/WRB). The document emphasizes transparency, confidentiality, and interoperability while detailing the data integration workflow from submission to validation and feedback. The CoW will also provide training and technical support, with protocols reviewed biennially to incorporate new technologies and stakeholder feedback.

Session 2 – Introduction to the SIS framework, FAIR data, and SIWF

Chrow Khurshid from ISRIC presented the SIS framework, gave a brief explanation, helping define ‘what is FAIR data?’ the [FAIR process framework](#), and why FAIR is good for soil data projects, and the [Soil Information Workflow](#). This followed by a Q&A session with the participants.

Session 3 – Introduction to the NiSIS Unit of ALCCMS at FMAFS

The presentation outlined the Data Integration Roadmap, launch-readiness of the Nigeria Farmers’ Soil Health Scheme (NFSHS), and partnership plans under the Coalition of the Willing (CoW) and Nigeria Soil Information System (NiSIS). It emphasizes the importance of soil health and data governance in alignment with Nigeria’s national development goals and global frameworks such as the SDGs and Paris Agreement. Key partners including AGRA, IITA, IFDC, and government agencies shared their contributions and commitments to strengthening NiSIS and supporting NFSHS implementation. The call-to-action urges stakeholders to share data, adopt standards, invest in NFSHS, promote inclusivity, and build sustainable partnerships.

A few key points were mentioned:

- There is a central repository for data storage and management in current NiSIS.
- Data is managed by the data unit team.
- No specific team member details were shared
- No specific NiSIS team structure and functions were shared.
- No strategy plan, capacity or funding plans for NiSIS team were shared.
- No details of capacity and DSM team members were shared.
- No clear stakeholders map was presented.
- No clear sustainable funding plan for NiSIS was presented.

Workshop Day 2:

Welcome and reflections from day one was led by Prof. Vincent, IITA, and supported by ISRIC.

Session 4 – Data requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the data challenges, and data agreements and mechanisms desired or in place. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- How should user permissions and data access be managed?
- What are the data challenges?
- What are the data requirements from user perspective?
- What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?
- How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?

How can the FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS?

Summary of group discussions:

Each of the seven groups (6-7 participants per group) used guiding questions to explore the topic. Key advice from all group discussions are summarized below:

1. Data Challenges

a. Technical Challenges

- Lack of digital infrastructure; many datasets remain paper-based.
- Non-standardized sampling designs, laboratory analyses, and instrumentation.
- Incomplete, duplicated, or inaccurate data with inconsistent formats.
- Weak quality control and limited reference samples.
- Poor data integration and lack of georeferencing for legacy datasets.

b. Human Capacity Challenges

- Shortage of qualified data scientists and technicians.
- Limited training opportunities.
- Low awareness of modern data management and sharing practices.

c. Institutional Challenges

- Weak or poorly implemented data policies.
- Data hoarding and limited inter-institutional collaboration.
- Poor staff motivation and lack of coordination among data producers.

d. Financial Challenges

- Inadequate funding for laboratories, GIS infrastructure, and data updates.
- Insufficient resources for equipment, reagents, and data upgrades.
- Absence of financial incentives to encourage data sharing.

e. Data Integrity and Ownership

- Undefined ownership and poor documentation of legacy data.
- Weak trust and lack of clear data-sharing protocols.
- No withdrawal or access control procedures.

2. Data Sharing, Access, and Policy

- Develop legally backed data-sharing agreements defining ownership, copyright, and liability.
- Protect sensitive/unpublished data with secure transfer mechanisms and controlled access.
- Create incentives for private and international data producers through recognition and visibility.
- Establish government policy frameworks to regulate sharing, auditing, and data use within NiSIS.
- Involve data-policy experts in governance and agreement formulation.

3. Plans and Strategies for Collaboration (National, International & Private Partners)

- Establish MoUs defining ownership, equity, and data-sharing principles.
- Encourage collaboration among local, international, and private organizations.
- Strengthen data privacy, security, and IP rights under the Nigeria Data Protection Act (2023).
- Ensure joint data accessibility through centralized platforms.
- Provide financial incentives and support capacity building for scientists.
- Enhance communication via media, social platforms, and public outreach.

4. Standardization and Metadata Management

- Develop national metadata standards and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for soil data.
- Host data on a centralized NiSIS server aligned with ISO/national standards.
- Review and update datasets every 3 years.
- Ensure interoperability and documentation across all institutions.
- Follow FAIR Data Principles.

5. Governance and Institutional Structure

- Create a NiSIS governance framework with a steering committee, technical committee, and secretariat.
- Define institutional roles and responsibilities in documentation.
- Ensure continuous coordination and review through focal committees.
- Enforce the Nigeria Data Protection Act (2023) and related legislation.
- Promote transparency and accountability in data governance.

6. Communication, Awareness, and Dissemination

- Develop policy briefs, media briefs, and press releases for policymakers.
- Organize seminars, workshops, and publications for researchers.
- Engage farmers and local users through extension agents, pamphlets, and training.
- Recognize and reward data contributors to promote sharing.

7. Building Trust and Data Sharing Culture

- Develop national policies mandating data sharing beyond institutional MoUs.
- Conduct sensitization campaigns to encourage collaboration.
- Promote cost-sharing, proper referencing, and co-publication among partners.

8. Data Use and Stakeholder Mapping

- Purpose: Teaching, research, investment planning, and policy formulation.
Outcomes:
 - Improved accessibility and real-time soil data availability.
 - Better-informed soil management policies and timely interventions.

9. Key Stakeholders:

Government ministries, universities, farmers, NGOs, SMEs, consultants, international organizations (FAO, UNDP, IITA, EU, IFAD, etc.), GIS specialists, and research institutes.

10. Data Requirements from Users

Users identified the following critical use cases and data needs:

- Slope and erosion risk.
- Soil water storage capacity.
- Soil texture and fertility levels.
- Heavy metal content.
- Topsoil depth and crop yield data.

11. Core Issues and Priority Actions

Core Issues:

- Poor data quality, limited access to data that should be stored in a central repository in NiSIS, lack of funding, weak governance, and inconsistent standards.

Priority Actions:

- Develop unified data standards and protocols.
- Strengthen institutional capacity and sustainable funding.
- Foster collaboration and communication among stakeholders.
- Enforce data governance and protection frameworks.
- Promote open, transparent, and incentive-based data sharing.

Session 5 – System Architecture & Technical Capacity

Note: Session 5 & 6 ran together, and suggestions were collected for both sessions at once due to limit time.

The objectives of this session were to explore future hosting of the SIS, considering what would be technically and organisationally feasible. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- System Architecture & Repository Design
 - Is there a central repository for data storage and management?
 - Who manages it (data unit team)?
 - What should be the Strategy/plan for consolidating data?

- Mapping Teams & Capacity
 - Identification of mapping teams (who they are, how many)?
 - What is the capacity for producing, interpreting and serving maps?
 - How will soil maps serve end users?

Session 6 - Long term sustainability- Technical & Strategic Discussions

Note: Session 5 & 6 ran together, and suggestions were collected for both sessions at once due to limit time.

The objective of this session was the alignment between system architecture and FAIR data principles and Integrating mapping outputs into NiSIS workflow to ensure the long-term sustainability of NiSIS. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Alignment between system architecture and FAIR data principles.**
 - How well does the current system architecture support Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR)?
 - What barriers exist (technical, institutional, financial) to implementing FAIR data principles in NiSIS?
 - How can metadata standards and data documentation be embedded into the system by design?
 - What governance mechanisms are needed to ensure long-term compliance with FAIR?
- **Integrating mapping outputs into NiSIS workflows**
 - What types of mapping outputs are most valuable for end users (e.g., soil fertility maps, land use, climate impact)?
 - How can mapping data be standardized and integrated into the NiSIS central repository?
 - What is the best way to ensure mapping products are regularly updated and validated?
 - How can mapping outputs be linked to other datasets (e.g., soil profiles, lab data) within NiSIS?
 - What tools or platforms are needed to make mapping outputs accessible and usable by policymakers, researchers, and farmers?

Summary of group discussions:

To outline key findings and policy recommendations emerging from the multi-group discussions (Seven Groups) on system architecture, data management, FAIR data and

sustainability of the National Soil Information System (NiSIS). Key insights from all groups are outlined below:

1. System Support for FAIR Data – Summary

- The existing data system aligns broadly with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) but requires stronger operationalization, governance, and compliance mechanisms. Major barriers include: limited technical expertise, inadequate ICT infrastructure, inconsistent data formats, weak institutional coordination, insufficient funding, and unclear legal and policy frameworks for data access and ownership.
- To strengthen FAIR implementation, metadata standards should be embedded “by design,” supported by unified SOPs, institutional databases, and regular capacity-building initiatives. Robust governance frameworks, including stewardship committees, M&E systems, and ideally national FAIR data policies, would be needed to ensure accountability and sustainability.
- Emphasis is placed on producing valuable mapping outputs (e.g., soil fertility, land use, erosion, irrigation, and climate maps) that directly inform agricultural and environmental decision-making. Data must be standardized, harmonized, and integrated across systems through centralized repositories and compatible software (e.g., SQL, PostgreSQL). Regular validation, updating, and stakeholder feedback are essential for data reliability.
- Integration of mapping outputs with other datasets should leverage GIS and open-source platforms, enabling interoperability across thematic areas. For accessibility, tools such as ArcGIS, WebGIS, mobile apps, USSD codes, and social media should be employed to reach both policymakers and local users. Persistent challenges include poor awareness, inconsistent methodologies, legacy data issues, weak data quality, limited sharing frameworks, and inadequate collaboration with international and private partners.

2. Key Findings by Thematic Area

A. Mapping Teams and Institutional Roles

- Composition: Soil scientists, GIS/RS experts, data analysts, field and extension workers.
- Institutions Involved: IAR&T, IAR, IITA, CDA, FMAFS, and universities (FUNAAB, UI, ABU, ATBU, UNIMAID, UNIJOS, etc.).
- Gaps: Uneven institutional capacity; limited technical expertise in GIS and data science.
- Policy Action:
 1. Strengthen institutional partnerships.
 2. Establish a national registry of certified mapping experts.

B. Capacity for Producing, Interpreting, and Serving Maps

- Current Strengths: Some institutions have good technical capacity and tools (ArcGIS, QGIS, ERDAS, ML tools).
- Challenges: Inadequate infrastructure, limited training, and insufficient funding for software/hardware.
- Policy Action:
 1. Institutionalize periodic capacity-building programs.
 2. Allocate dedicated budget lines for GIS and digital infrastructure.
 3. Promote technology sharing among research and government institutions.

C. End-User Relevance and Service Delivery

- Applications: Agricultural planning, crop suitability, irrigation mapping, fertilizer recommendations, drought/erosion monitoring.
- Accessibility: Maps should be user-friendly, interactive, and location-specific.
- Policy Action:
 1. Develop multi-platform access (web, mobile, USSD, offline apps).
 2. Encourage community-based data engagement and feedback loops.

D. Data Consolidation and Management

- Core Processes: Data extraction → cleaning & standardization → validation → uploading into repositories.
- Framework Needs: National data policy, standardized templates, metadata protocols, and clear ownership of data.
- Policy Action:
 1. Create a National Soil Data Framework and Central Repository.
 2. Mandate data sharing MOUs among institutions.
 3. Establish a taskforce or regulatory body for data compliance and quality assurance.

E. Barriers to Implementation

Type	Challenges Identified	Recommended Policy Response
Technical	Lack of standards, weak FAIR compliance, poor power supply	Develop and enforce data & metadata standards; improve infrastructure
Institutional	Undefined roles, weak governance, poor coordination	Establish clear governance structures and accountability mechanisms

Financial	Inadequate funding, weak fund management	Secure sustained budgetary allocations and improve financial transparency
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F. Tools and Integration Platforms

- Platforms: Web portals, mobile apps (offline), USSD, SMS, and APIs for cross-system integration (e.g., NISS, METSADA, NASGAP).
- Policy Action: Encourage open-source, interoperable platforms and require data providers to publish accessible APIs.

G. Standards, Monitoring, and Evaluation

- Requirements: Standardized data collection and documentation processes; automated M&E systems; continuous validation.
- Policy Action:
 1. Establish national M&E teams for soil data.
 2. Adopt a unified national standard for soil data documentation.
 3. Automate validation using data integration software.

H. Governance and Sustainability

- Needs: National policy coherence, capacity-building framework, stakeholder collaboration.
- Policy Action:
 1. Develop a national soil data governance framework.
 2. Embed FAIR data principles in all national soil programs.
 3. Schedule data validation and updates every 3 years.

Summary of Priority Actions

- Create a centralized national soil data repository with standardized formats.
- Institutionalize capacity development in GIS, metadata management, and FAIR principles.
- Ensure multi-stakeholder coordination through a taskforce or steering committee.
- Mandate data sharing and integration across platforms via APIs.
- Allocate dedicated funding for infrastructure and software.
- Develop automated monitoring and evaluation systems for continuous improvement.

Session 7- Development of Standardized SOPs

The objective of this session was to explore the development of standardized SOPs for field sampling and laboratory analysis. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the current practices for field sampling and lab analysis across different institutions?
- Where do we see inconsistencies or gaps in existing SOPs?
- Which international or regional standards could we align with?
- What minimum requirements should a uniform SOP include to ensure quality and comparability of data?
- What challenges might arise in adopting standardized SOPs, and how can we address them?
- How can we ensure stakeholder buy-in and compliance with the new SOPs?
- What resources (training, tools, infrastructure) are needed to support implementation?

Summary of group discussions:

Seven groups (each with 7-9 participants) discussed the SOPs to be adopted by NiSIS. The key findings are summarized below:

1. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that agreed upon by all participants during the workshop:

- Field Sampling: Use S4A, FAO guidelines, AfSIS protocol, and other project-based SOPs.
- Encourage harmonization across national projects.
- Laboratory Analysis: Apply GLOSOLAN, AOAC, and ITA standards. Adopt project-based SOPs where necessary, ensuring consistency.

2. Current Gaps

- Lack of harmonized national SOPs and uneven adoption of international standards.

3. International/Regional Standards to adapt in NiSIS

- Recognized standards include GLOSOLAN (Lab), AOAC (Lab), AfSIS/S4A/AUSO (Field and Lab).

4. Challenges

- Low awareness and limited access to protocols.
- Insufficient hands-on training and inadequate laboratory or field equipment.

5. Recommended Actions

- Conduct workshops and practical training (lab and field).
- Increase access to current protocols.
- Adapt and align national SOPs with international standards.

6. Resource Needed

- Training and capacity development.
- Infrastructure improvement.
- Modern analytical tools and technologies.

Session 8 - Next steps

Below questions were used to identify the next steps for NiSIS with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions?
- Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each?
- Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured?
- What are the key milestones for NiSIS over the next 6, 12 and 24 months?

The actions are provided in the table below.

Table 1 Action points

Action point	Account-able (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Respon-sible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Development of policy draft for NiSIS	FMAFS	ALCCMS	CoW	November 2025	1	Policy for NFSHS
Further develop the RA- CoW, for data, lab, field,	ALCCMS	MIS TEAM	CoW	November 2025	1	Ready portal for users

technical, policy assessment						
Development of data policy, data sharing agreement, review and improvements of the current sharing protocol	ALCCMS	CoW	CoW	December 2025	1	Final draft of policy and data sharing agreement
MoU between IITA & FMAFS	DG IITA/HMS	ALCCMS	IITA/FMAFS	December 2025	1	Long term partnership
SIS development roadmap report-review	ISRIC	ALCCMS/NTT	IITA	December 2025-January 2026	1	Roadmap for further developing NiSIS
Readiness NFSHS-NiSIS by the states	State ministry of agriculture	STEC	state / CoW level	November 2025-March 2026	1	Buy-in by the states
SOPs for labs and field sampling	IITA/HUB	NISS, SSSN	IITA, ALCCMS	March 2026	1	National standardized SOPs
Improve NiSIS portal	ALCCMS	ALCCMS, MIS Team	Hub, ISRIC	June 2026	1	International standard NiSIS portal
Capacity building on different domains in NiSIS	FMAFS	ALCCMS	Hub, ISRIC, CoW	June-December 2026	1	Ready team

National soil survey/NOT	FMAFS	ALCCMS	Hub, CoW	Nov 2025- Dec 2026	1	Recommendation
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Annex 1: Workshop Program

NiSIS Roadmap Development Workshop Programme

Day 1: 21 October – Setting the Scene			
Time	Session	Content & Speakers	NFSHS/NiSIS Alignment
08:00 – 09:00	Registration		
09:00 – 11:30	Session 1: Opening & Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome by Moderator - FMAFS Welcome: Need for SIS (Director ALCCMS-FMAFS) - Goodwill Messages (OCP, GIZ, Soil Values, IAR&T, SSSN) - AfSIS/NiSIS beginning (Mr. Ojuola, Profs. Amapu & Vincent) - NiSIS current state (Prof. James) - Soil health cards link (Prof. Jibrin) - The Regional Hub (Prof. Vincent) - Workshop overview (Dr. Chow) - IITA DDG R4D welcome message (Dr. Bernard Vanlauwe) - Keynote Address: Data integration roadmap, and SIS partnerships (Sen. Dr. Aliyu Sabi Abdullahi, CON, Baraden Borgu, HMS, FMAFS) 	Position NiSIS as backbone for soil data integration under NFSHS; link soil health cards to state-level NFSHS rollouts.
11:30 – 12:15	Group Photograph/Tea Break		
12:30 – 13:30	LUNCH		
13:30 – 15:00	Session 2: SIS Framework & FAIR Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISRIC Presentation: SIS Framework, FAIR principles, Soil Information Workflow (SIWF) - Q&A 	CoW WG1: Embed FAIR principles into NFSHS data management (labs, blending plants, state datasets).
15:00 – 15:30	Tea Break		
15:30 – 16:30	Session 3: MoU (FMAFS/IITA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FMAFS Presentation: Team structure & functions - National Technical Team (NTT) - Understanding MoU (FMAFS/IITA) 	CoW WG3: Mirror governance with State Technical Executive Committees for NFSHS readiness & rollout.
16:30 – 17:00	Day 1 Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reflections (FMAFS, IITA, ISRIC) - Official closure 	CoW role: Facilitate subnational adoption of NiSIS protocols for NFSHS.

Day 2: 22 October – Building for Integration			
Time	Session	Content / Speakers	CoW – NFSHS Alignment
09:00 – 10:30	Session 4: Data Requirements & Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recap of Day 1 - Identify challenges, access, policies, user needs - Discussion: data sharing, FAIR principles 	CoW WG1: Apply CoW Data-Sharing Protocols (CSV, Shapefile, WGS84, ISO metadata) for harmonized state-level contributions to NiSIS & NFSHS.
10:30 – 11:00	Tea Break		
11:00 – 12:30	Session 5: System Architecture & Technical Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repository design - Mapping teams & capacity - Data consolidation strategy 	CoW WG1 & WG4: Link system design to NFSHS Soil Health Cards , digital fertilizer advisory tools, and soil fertility maps.
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 – 15:00	Session 6: Sustainability – Technical & Strategic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FAIR data compliance & governance - Mapping outputs integration - Strategic planning for long-term NiSIS 	CoW WG4: Showcase innovations (FertiChar, HEFE FMAFS, Growbeit) as use-cases; strengthen global linkages (AfSIS, GloSIS, FAO).
15:00 – 15:30	Tea Break		
15:30 – 16:30	Session 7: Standardized SOPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harmonize field sampling & lab analysis - Align with international/regional standards 	CoW WG2: Adopt uniform SOPs for NFSHS labs; train soil health desk officers; partner with universities for sustained capacity building.
16:30 – 17:30	Session 8: Next Steps & Action Items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consolidate insights - Set short, medium, and long-term milestones (6, 12, 24 months) - Assign responsibilities & accountability 	CoW WG3: Establish State TECs for NFSHS , mobilize advocacy/financing, and assign CoW monitoring roles for soil data integration.
17:30 – 17:45	Day 2 Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Takeaways (FMAFS, Hub, ISRIC) - Closing remarks 	CoW positioned as strategic driver for NiSIS–NFSHS integration nationwide.

Day 3: 23 October – Fertilizer Trials & Workshop Assessment			
Time	Activity	Lead	
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome	ALCCMS-FMAFS/IITA/ISRIC	
9:30 – 10:00	Tea Break		
10:00 – 12:30	Session 1: Generating fertilizer recommendations Session 2: Status of NOT Session 3: Piloting virtual agronomy	Siyabusa, Romaric & Surajit, Tofa Jibrin & Vincent	

12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 – 14:30	Technical & data infrastructure assessment form	Chrow, ISRIC	
14:30 – 15:30	Lab discussion	Uponi Joseph	
15:30 – 16:00	Tea Break		
16:30 – 17:00	Closing remarks	ALCCMS-FMAFS/IITA/ISRIC	

Annex 2: Flipcharts from different groups

Group F
Data Requirements

1. Data Challenges

- Variability in Methodologies:
 - * Sampling Methods
 - * Analysis Methods/ procedures
 - * Reporting Methods/ units
- Traceability:
 - * Ungeoreferenced legacy data
 - * Method of georeferencing
- Method of ^{data} storage
- Variability in number of Parameters Per dataset

2. Plans for International and Private Partners (data producers)

There is need proper Motivation for data Producers:

- * Visibility of data producers (Acknowledgement)
- * Access to training/ capacity building for data producers
- * Acknowledging co-creators

3. Section A. 7 quor2

Include name of head of Institution

Section B
There should be options or areas to be committed to

Section C
Remove focal points, let name alone remain

Group D - Data

Q1) ~~What are the challenges~~ Requirements

- a) Standardize data not seldomly available (methods, units & reporting format)
- b) Willingness to share data (Lack of willingness to share data) due to no recognition
- c) Fragmented data
- d) Resources for sourcing data

Q2) What is the Plan for International & Private Partners

- a) Providing incentive under agreed terms.
- b) Open data stack
- c) Creating AWARENESS FOR DATA POLICY

Q3)

Group D

Q3) a) THE BENEFITS TO THE COALITION PARTNERS ARE NOT MENTIONED.

b) REQUEST FOR DATA NOT REFLECTED.

Group B

DATA REQUIREMENTS

Q1 Data Challenges

- What's my gain?
- 3rd party accessibility to stored data without due diligence
- Intellectual Property
- Capacity development of data collectors

Q2

- Data-sharing agreement (legally backed)
- For Private Organisations (No 100% funding by them)
- Clearly statement of the conditions in the MoU/data sharing agreement
- Govt policy on data sharing
 - * Any data generated in Nigeria, the Govt should have access to the data
 - * The data must carry the logo of the source
- Secured data transfer Mechanism
- Process for monitoring, & processing & auditing partner data practices

Group B

Q3 Review of Col form

- Decision-making on data use
- who retains the ownership/copyright of the data
- Any liability/legal implications of signing the form
- Protection of sensitive or un-published data.
- Data-policy experts should be involved in the discussion of datasets

GROUP A

Q1. What Barriers exist?

- * Inadequate technical personnel
- * Inadequate funding
- * Institutional Policies
- * Lack of accessibility / Data hoarding

Q2 How can metadata standards & data documentation be embedded into the system?

- Data cleaning in conformity to global Standard (Standardization, Validation & Transformation)

Q3 What governance mechanism are needed?

- Establish governance structure for Nisis
 - a. Steering Committee
 - b. Technical committee
 - c. Secretariat Committee

Q4. What types of mapping are most valuable?

- Soil fertility maps
- Climate impact maps

GROUP A

Q5. How can mapping data be standardized?

- Uniformity in Software design

Q6 What is the best way to ensure mapping products are regularly updated?

- There should be time line (minimum of 2 years and maximum of 5 years)

Q7 How can mapping outputs be linked?

- * The web design should be robust to accommodate all the different soil data categories.

Q8 What tools or platforms are needed, to make mapping outputs accessible?

- Through web sites.
- Email addresses
- Social medias etc / Communication Link to the maps

Group A

Q1 CHALLENGES (DATA)

- * Limited resources/funding
- * Data hoarding / Limited accessibility
- * Non-uniformity of data Coalition

Q2 PLAXI FOR INTERNATIONAL & PRIVATE PARTNERS (DATA PRODUCERS)

- Awareness of CoM - social media - Ext Agents
- Partnership with local & International Organizations that have & willing to join CoM
- Joint accessibility to data
- Funding
- Capacity building

4

Data Requirement 2

Data policies, strategies and management mandates exist

- No high level policy
- Only MOU between Institutions and Consultants

Data sharing can be achieved between SCS related efforts by -

1. High-Level Policy to mandate individuals
2. Data sharing agreements betw National & International Partners & Approval by the government
3. Sensitization on the need for data sharing & Collaboration.

Building Trust for Data Sharing

- Cost sharing / on national level
- Recognition & proper referencing of data sources
- Co-publication

Group C / Stakeholders maps

Q1.

- * 1. Gearing of Research
- 2. Gap Identification
- 3. Investment planning
- 4. Effective research management

Q2.

- 1. Increased accessibility to soil data
- 2. Availability to soil data (Real time data, Soil resource)
- 3. Formulation of sound policies on soil management.
- 4. Timely & Site Specific government / donor support response

Vision

* Nation platform for accessing data on soil

Q3. Availability & Accessibility of Creditable data on soil to policies makers

GROUP C Stakeholders maps ①

Q4.

AND Environmental consultants - Producer ~~F&S~~

- 2. Universities / Academic Institution - P/U
- 3. Small / medium scale Interpro. (SME) P/U
- 4. Local Farmers - User
- 5. NGOs - Producer
- 6. Ministries of Environment & Climate Change (EPA) (SME) P/U
- 7. GIS-Specialist - P/U
- 8. Research Inst - Like SLURC - P/U
- 9. FAO/UNDP/IITA/EU/IFAD → Funders

Group C Data Requirements

Q1.

- 1. Creation of user account

Q2.

- 1. Past data not digitized
- 2. Fragmentation of soil data
- 3. Unwillingness to share data
- 4. Inaccessibility to raw data

Q3.

- 1. Clean data / Creditable useful
- 2. - Standardized data.

Q4. National digital development policy 2020

- 2. National digital development Strategy
- 3. Geo-data management policy.
- 4. Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative
- Open data policy 2016

GROUP-C

- 4. ~~Cyber Security & Cyber Crimes Act~~
- 5. Developing data protection policy
- 5. Right to Access Information Act 2013

Q5. Development & Signing of MoUs

Q6. Stakeholder should follow the "FAIR" Framework

- F - Findable
- A - Accessible
- I - Interoperable
- R - Reusable

Involvement of key staff

Group B

- UC: Soil health, buy on policy makers & soil management, ecosystem stability, enhancing collaboration, advancing agriculture productivity, identifying Areas prone to land slides, erosion, based on their soil structure & looking land use planning, economic valleys, crop suitability mapping, monitor soil fertility, soil management on farm level, fertilizer recommendations
- Yes + all future soil info should go there
 - MAFS work with universities & states & research institutes.
 - data sharing policies.
 - providing centralize resources for various actors to better understand SL soils.
 - one stop shop
 - self sustainable & data of interest & monitor that data. (link to SIS)
 - stronger policies in place on the soil.
 - desire on policy on data collection → along with soil survey.
 - efficient use of farmer input & natural resources.
 - understanding the soil predictability with climate change.
- see above.
 - agronomic data - soil variability → all help in policies
 - Data in MAFS → can be analysed to inform decision makes
 - Awareness raising is important.
 - level of farmers are supported by improved yield.

Group B

National fertilizer regulation agencies

- Bankers → cost info could evaluate loan applications to farmers → thus you are not high risk agro dealers or input dealers → to have better info of fertilizer return to farmers
- Seed: Sileco → to use for seed recommendations
- Investors → to know status of soil farmers → for site specific recomms.
- Construction companies for geo technical advice.
- Research institutions → Environmental Scientist, SEPA environmental protection Agency, CEAS.
- Sierra Leone Water Company (works under National water authority planners)

MAFSA planners can use & provide data.

data challenges:

- data permission.
- key stakeholder role should be defined: access (for only users), or who determine
- Raw data should be accessible to anyone (should be de-identified, like CoCo)
- But you can not suddenly upload data - cause that needs to quality check
- go through process before it's uploaded.
- may be limited you must agree can access in time - if you can no down it so much permission
- registered user to agree how what's going on
- MAFSA are developing tool in data etc
- MAFSA have access to all data. If you want in depth data you can request MAFSA/SEPA and pay for it
- clear data should be centralized platform
- Data ownership and permission
- There should be one contact person for system to send request.

Group B

Some data should be open in systems, but not all. At the data are restricted/limited to actors.

Large should be there → so users are restricted.

One centralized system so you can see what is in system → so everyone has maximum

- to use should be able to put in subsidiary
- to adapt users can → but you need way for depth analysis
- to use restricted

You need set data policies for system.

Once you have system, you can reach out to universities → they can login for free if they share their data for

- data challenges:
 - integrated data: data format issues, metadata in missing, lack of skilled people to manage data, cost of cloud system
 - not digitized data: stored locally on computers, supporting the data in looking into future use.
 - data linked in not same: data management system, accountability, data sharing culture → policies.
- standards:
 - We need to select standard → FAO for watershed
 - transparency is important to build trust
- Policy:
 - struggle to access information (not have name)
 - update infrastructure, as policies in place, specify for on site or place
 - many of agriculture (not have)
 - clear mapping of information might have some policies in place for data sharing
 - Ministry of environment have already some structure in place for data sharing
 - it can be use to SL
 - to may use building infrastructure → they might capacity
 - to update, can get data
- user permission:
 - clear data sharing agreement.
 - update infrastructure mandate or clarify which data goes to environment → also for agriculture → training
 - to use user data?
 - clear user permission in system.
 - to user data can be used for
 - to policy maker a common standard is important → metadata, centralized data platform, transparency.
 - to resource data is important, hence agreed on.

Group A

Stakeholder Map / requirements

- * Essential use cases for the SIS
- Land management
- Specific crop recommendation
- Fertilizer formulation
- Crop water use efficiency
- Assessment of soil health/soil degradation status
- Environmental management - climate change adaptation.
- Research purpose

Outcomes

The desired outcome and long-term vision of SIS - Co-hosting - SLARI/NU

- Evidence based policy formation
- Efficient Use of Soil resources
- Improved Agronomic practices
- Enhanced sustainable crop production

Group A

Sierra Leone's Agricultural policy

- Fertilizer regulation
- Land use planning

Other stakeholders

- MAFS
- Farmers
- MGO's
- CEDAS/EPA
- NAFRA

Group A

Data Requirements?

- FAIR data principle - creative commons
- * recommendations (permission needs to be obtained for every use cases).

Data challenges

- Data format
- Temporal dynamics of soil data
- Data sharing culture (poor)
- Limited Data/Fragmented data
- Limited digital data collection capacity
- Poor Collaboration

Data Requirements from the user perspective

- Slope - Soil fertility levels
- Erosion risk - Top soil depth
- Soil water storage capacity
- Soil texture - crop yield
- Heavy metal content

- (1)
Group C

 1. How does the current structure support FAIR
 - The current system architecture is FAIR
 2. What barriers exist to implementing FAIR
 - Technical - The technical know-how
 - Infrastructure (ICT)
 - SOPs
 - Institutional - Lack of the political will to implement existing policies
 - Lack of synergy at the institutional level
 - Administrative bottlenecks
 - Financial - poor budgeting/Implementation
 3. How can metadata & data documentation be embedded into the system and upload (conversion of raw data to metadata)
 - Convert into an acceptable format
 4. Governance Mechanisms
 - Transparency, sustainability, continuity, accountability, inclusiveness with M&E
 5. What types of mapping outputs are most valuable for the end users
 - Land Use, Soil fertility maps & climate
 6. How mapping data can be standardized and integrated
 - Clean, Correlate and Integrate

(2)
Group C

 7. The best way to ensure mapping products are regularly updated and validated
 - Stakeholders feedback and evaluation
 - Constitution of a committee for M&E
 8. How mapping outputs can be linked to other datasets
 - Can be superimposed by using the appropriate softwares
 9. What tools or platforms are needed to make mapping outputs accessible
 - Social media handles
 - Policy briefs
 - Publications (possibly into local languages)
 - Mobile Apps

Group G
Data Challenges

- * Awareness
 - * Inconsistencies in analytical procedures & Sampling Methods
 - * Georeferencing of legacy datasets
 - * Data Quality
 - * Data format & unit
 - * Cost of cleaning & harmonization
 - * Accessibility
- Provisions for International & private partners

- * Sensitization of relevant stakeholders
- * Data protection & privacy regulation.
- * Drafting and Moll

Group G
Review of Declaration form.

- * Specify the technical expertise required
- * Specify the data type needed
- * Consequences for non-adherence.

GRUPE.

Alignment w/ System Arch and FAIR data Prin.

1. What barriers exist to (imp. technical, inst; financial) to implementing FAIR data Principle on NISIS.
 - Technical:-
 - Internet Infrastructure - eg. bandwidth, internet storage/backups etc.
 - Internet connectivity, prefer fibre than wifi within the repository, power supply.
 - Software interoperability/compatibility.
 - Institutional:-
 - Shortage SKILL personal
 - Infrastructure:- Compa, Power supply, conducive office space.
 - bureaucratic processes.
 - Financial:-
 - Insufficient budgetary provision
 - Timeliness & fund release.
 - Inadequate support from development partners.
2. How can Metadata Standards, and data documentation doc embedded into the system by design.
 - SOP design only accept specified and agreed SOP.
 - The SOP must be clearly defined, through stakeholder workshop
 - The doc SPECIFIC data type for documentation.
3. What governance mechanisms are needed for to ensure long-term compliance with FAIR.
 - External compliance mechanisms are needed for to ensure
 - Regular review & adherence FAIR data policy.
4. What type of mapping outputs are valuable for end users.
 - Land maps (detailed)
 - Soil nutrient maps
 - Land suitability maps.
 - Land evaluation maps.
5. How can mapping data be shared and integrated into the NISIS central repository.
 - Activation of the committee on Standardization and Validation
 - Activation of Committee on Correlation and Harmonization

- a6. What is best way to ensure mapping products are regularly updated and validated?
 - Regular Review and updating (27M).
 - Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E).
- a7. How can Mapping outputs be linked to other datasets (eg soil profiles, lab data).
 - > Using Geo databases eg SDG; postgres SQL
- a8. What tools or platforms are need to make mapping outputs Access and Useable by policy makers, Research and farmers-
 - Web GIS
 - Mobile apps
 - links use easily share available on social media
 - formal extension agent,
 - Use USSD Code.

SOP ①

- Field Sampling
 - FAO guidelines
 - AFSIS Protocol
 - Project Based SOPs
- Lab Analysis
 - GLOSOLAN
 - Project Based SOPs
 - IITA Manual
- Gaps in SOPs

NOTE

- International or Regional Standards
 - GLOSOLAN
 - AOAC - LAB.
 - AU SO - African Union Soil (from EU SO & UK SO) Observatory - Field & Lab
 - SAA / AFSIS - Field

SOP ②

- Challenges ⇒ How to Address them
 - Increased Awareness
 - Workshops
 - ~~Hands On~~ Training on the SOP (Lab + Field)
 - Equipments

- Buy-in
 - Access the current protocols
 - Adapt what align to the International Standards

- Resources
 - Training
 - Infrastructure
 - Tools

GROUP F

Sustainability for Technical & Strategic Discussions

- Barriers on implementation of fair data
 - Lack of Universal Unique ID - Need for barcodes and Standards
 - Lack of policy that ensures FAIR data principle
 - Lack of Offline access to data
 - Unstable power supply
- How to incorporate standards & data documentation into the system
 - Standardized templates for data collection, compilation & transmission
 - Insistence on WGS 84 Coordinate Ref. System
- Governance Mechanism
 - Robust policy that ensure compliance
 - Continuous monitoring & review of the FAIR
- Mapping Outputs most valuable to farmers:
 - Soil Fertility Map
 - Crop Suitability Map
 - Land Use Maps → Erosion Vulnerability Map
 - Crop & Site specific fertilizer recommendations
 - Drought Vulnerability Maps
- Integrating data into NISIS Central Repository
 - Standardized templates with uniform templates to be uploaded into the central hub
- Regular updating and validation
 - Fixing regular intervals for updating & validation say like 3 years.

GROUP F

- Linking mapping Outputs to other datasets
 - Provision should be made in the NISIS platform for linking up with other datasets (satellite)
 - e.g. NIMET, NISADA, G-NAGSAP
 - The data provider should make available their API (Application Program Interface)
- Tools and platforms needed to make Mapping Outputs accessible
 - USSD Codes
 - Web-base
 - Mobile APP (Offline mobile APP)
 - Community-base engagement
 - Bulletin

GROUP "D" - DATA ARCHITECTURE

Q1- Identification of mapping teams (who they are, how many)?

Research Institutes - IARST, IAR, Private - OCP Africa, Universities - UDUS, FUNAAB, ATBU, UI, UNIMAD, FUTMINA, UNIJOS, CDA/BUK

Q2- What is the capacity for Producing, Interpreting & Serving maps?

Organisations	Fair	Good	V. Good	Excellence
IARST		✓		
IAR		✓		
OCP				
CDA	✓			
UDUS, ATBU, UI, UNIMAD, UNIJOS		✓		
FUNAAB				

Q3- How can maps serve end users?

- Land use Planning (Irrigation scheme, forest monitoring, Land Capability Suitability)
- Crop & Soil specific fertilizer formulation & recommendations
- Monitoring of Soil degradation

Q4- What should be the strategy/Plan for consolidating data?

- Capacity development in data collection & management
- National data framework Policy
- MOU framework for data collection & management with COW partners.

Group B: SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Q1: - Depends on the objectives of the project, software, expertise & datasets to be collected. How many? depends on the size of the project.

Q2: - Depends on the availability of funds, expertise, tools and infrastructures

Q3: - Depends the legendary information provided on the map and the end-user

Q4: - Validation of the data, capacity building for users and managers. The stakeholders should co-create the map (standardize). There should be a structure ⇒ from generator → data manager (cleaning, validation) → end users

- Strategy: - define the ownership of the data

- set clear objectives for consolidating the data.

GROUP B ALIGNMENT BTW SYS ARCHITECTURE & FAIR

Q2: Technical: (i) Lack of expertise to set up the platform. Hence, there's need to depend on international organisations
 (ii) Lack of standard for metadata collection

Institutional: (i) No clear policy & protocol on who does what where and when
 (ii) Lack of capacity development for staff
 (iii) Lack of fund management principles by the institutions

Financial: (i) Lack of will to use the funds for the right purposes
 (ii) Lack of funding (inadequate funding)
 (iii) Lack of readiness on the part of the institutions

Q3: (i) There should be an agreed process for standardization
 (ii) Automation of the process e.g capturing, processing, storage, maintenance and retrieval.
 (iii) creation of data library (Repository), definition of terms and terminologies = Data documentation tools.

Q4: (i) Setting up of taskforce/regulatory body for compliance
 (ii) Incentives for all stakeholders should be clearly stated

Q5: Depends on the interest of the end-users, all the listed outputs e.g soil fertility map, land use & climate impact are all intertwined.

GROUP B CONTINUES

Q6: The established standard should be followed strictly.

Q7: - Have a functioning monitoring & evaluation team. This can be automated.
 - Adopt a common standard.

Q8: should be automated using data integration software

Q9: Softwares, Apps & interactive maps etc.

GROUP A
 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Q1 Identification of Mapping Team

- * The experts such as
 - Pedologist
 - Geospatial personnel
 - Data Analyst
- * Depending on area of coverage

Q2 What is capacity to produce Interpret and Issue Maps

- Technical expertise
- Field Workers
- Funding
- Extension workers
- End users

Q3 How can Map serve end users

- It should be user friendly
- It should ~~have~~ ^{be} location specific

Q3

- It should be ~~easy~~ self explanatory.

Q4 What should be the strategy / Plan for consolidating data

- ✓ Data extraction (Spreadsheet, Cloud, Flat file etc)
- ✓ Data transformation (Cleaning, & Standardization)
- ✓ Data uploading

GROUP - G SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

- * Identification of digital mapping teams
- Soil Scientist, GIS experts, Laboratory analyst & Data Scientist.
- * Capacity for producing, interpreting & serving maps
- Map production: IARAT, IITA, CDA & FMAFS
- Interpretation: All the listed institutions
- Serving maps: IARAT, FUNABAC, CDA

→ How can maps serve end users

- Agricultural planning & Management
- Know soil types & fertility status
- Soil suitability for specific crops
- Site specific fertilizer recommendations.
- Identification of erosion & flood prone areas
- Identification of irrigation capability
- Clear objectives
- Identifying origin of data source
- Data quality assessment & validation.
- Data repository & Capacity building

GROUP E System Architecture

Q1. Strategy/plan for consolidating data?

- Coll to share data
- Incentives for data sharing
- Central aggregation
- Standardized formats
- Define purpose & scope

Q2. How can maps serve the end user?

- Loading on website
- Interactive maps
- Language extension workers
- User friendliness / APP with interactive features

Q3. Identification of mapping team?

- GIS expert / soil scientist / data scientist
- 36 professionals / 1st trainees (18000)
- 2. Soil map:
 - Production - 36 / 36 tractors
 - cartography 36
 - classification 36
 - 36 information experts 36
 - Data Scientist 36
 - (including 18000)

Q4. Capacity for producing, interpreting & serving maps?

<p>production / need to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - software expert - R system - application - GIS / prod / GIS - machine learning eg RF, ANN - Application team <p>few available</p>	<p>interpretation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Software for fertilizer management - ERDAS Imagine - Arc GIS / Pro GIS - * few / medium available across
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Serving maps

- expertise in web GIS required
- technical infrastructure eg server / website development / computer developer team

GROUP F System Architecture

- The digital mapping teams
 - They are GIS / RS Unit of FMAFS
 - They are over 30 staff
- Capacity for producing, interpreting & serving maps
 - Personnel available
 - There is need for further training / Capacity building
 - Funding for GIS tools (Software, hardware)
 - Support development of predictive models
- How maps will serve end users
 - Evidence-based information for policy / decision making
 - Baseline information for further development of SIS
 - Guide agricultural land use planning
 - Crop suitability / better land use practices
 - Crop & site specific fertilizer recommendations
- Strategies / Plan for fertilizer recommendation
 - Formalizing soil data guidance and sharing policy
 - Data standardization
 - Harmonizing different datasets.

Group C - System Architecture

- Identification of Digital mapping teams
 - WHO THEY ARE
 - GIS EXPERTS, CARTOGRAPHIC DATA SCIENTISTS
 - IN UNIVERSITIES RESEARCH INST. & PRI COMPANIES
 - HOW MANY? requires a study/poll to ascertain that.
- CAPACITY FOR PRODUCING, INTERPRETING & SERVING MAPS
 - PRODUCTION - capacity exist for data acquisition, cleaning, analysis and cringing
 - Interpretation - Capacity exist number not known but additional training and capacity building needed
 - Serving - Capacity exist to show map on selected platforms
- HOW MAP CAN SERVE END USERS
 - user friendliness
 - putting it in a language farmers understand
 - through workshops & conferences
 - mobile apps for stations
 - Fertilizer companies for fertilizer blending

* WHAT SHOULD BE THE STRATEGY / PLAN FOR CONSOLIDATING DATA

- Capacity building for experts
- periodic review of data
- Generating more data
- Transformation into useful formats and forms
- Succession plan of experts

GROUP C

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